

An Automated Testing and Orchestration Framework for Softwarized 5G and B5G Network Applications

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Abstract—The evolution of 5G and B5G networks is revolutionizing mobile communications and enabling new use cases. Consequently, vertical industries are relying more on advanced applications that can leverage the potential of such innovations – the so-called Network Applications. However, testing frameworks for these advanced Network Applications remain scarce, limiting the adoption of such applications. This work proposes a framework to orchestrate, test, and validate these applications, introducing specific test cases to validate their functionality.

Index Terms—5G, B5G, Testing, Orchestration, Network Applications, Validation, Automation

I. INTRODUCTION

5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) Networks represent a major shift in mobile communications, improving bandwidth, latency, and connectivity for services like autonomous vehicles and remote healthcare. These technologies rely significantly on Network Function Virtualization (NFV), which decouples Network Functions (NFs) from hardware, offering increased flexibility, scalability, and lower costs. [1].

To enable novel use cases, various industries are developing 5G Network Applications (N.Apps). These applications are mainly softwarized solutions designed to run on virtualized environments within 5G infrastructures. N.Apps can be compared to the Open RAN (O-RAN) eXtended Applications (xApps) leveraged by a Radio Access Network (RAN) Intelligent Controller (RIC) to simplify and automate the management and control of the RAN. Similarly to xApps, N.Apps can interact with the 5G Core Control Plane to perform control and management operations aimed at optimizing the 5G Network for the use cases offered by such applications. An example of a N.App is a Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) application that monitors wildfires through video streams made available by various cameras installed in a forest. In the presence of a wildfire, this PPDR N.App can request additional bandwidth to the 5G Network, and thus increase the video streams quality.

By leveraging Network Function Virtualization (NFV), N.Apps deliver tailored, scalable, and flexible services to various vertical industries, such as the automotive one [2]. Additionally, when 6G networks become commercially available, 5G N.Apps will be adapted to leverage 6G, delivering even more advanced and efficient services.

As vertical industries depend more on Network Applications, reliability and performance become crucial. Given the roles N.Apps play in sectors such as autonomous driving, smart manufacturing, and public safety, rigorous testing is essential to validate their functionality and robustness, ensuring they meet quality standards and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) [3].

Additionally, testing aids in identifying potential vulnerabilities and performance bottlenecks, ensuring stability and efficiency before N.Apps deployment, which builds trust among users and providers. Consequently, comprehensive testing methodologies and frameworks are crucial in the N.App development lifecycle. However, these methodologies and frameworks are still scarce, hindering the widespread adoption of N.Apps, as developers cannot fully evaluate their performance, interoperability, and security in controlled settings.

This work proposes a comprehensive framework for testing and validating 5G N.Apps. Our methodology revolves around 5G N.Apps, but can easily be adapted for B5G/6G networks, thus being valuable to the scientific and industrial communities. Our work thoroughly addresses the various complexities of orchestrating and testing Network Applications, introducing an automated approach to expedite these processes.

II. RELATED WORK

Organizations such as the European Commission (EC), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), and Linux Foundation (LF) recognize that new methodologies for the testing and validation of 5G N.Apps are required. While ETSI pushes for the standardization of NFV technologies, the EC continuously sponsors novel research projects like 5G-IANA and Smart5Grid to develop testing and validation methods. Additionally, the Linux Foundation promotes novel N.App orchestration and testing methodologies through the Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP), initially founded by AT&T and China Mobile [4].

Regarding the validation of 5G N.Apps, several authors are working toward defining and providing fully automated platforms capable of orchestrating these applications and conduct a variety of tests on them. These platforms address various workflows: (i) onboarding N.App artifacts, (ii) their orchestration, and (iii) the orchestration of the tests that shall be performed on the N.Apps. Moreover, the orchestration process can assume two scenarios: one where the deployments take place in a single facility, and a distributed one, where N.App components are split across multiple facilities, thus considering the application a multi-domain one. Multi-domain applications, as well as their testing processes, are far more complex since one must deal with the intricacies of orchestrating a distributed application and conduct distributed testing processes.

For offering 5G Network Applications, some authors rely on NFV standards, while others offer them as cloud-native applications. For instance, the EVOLVED-5G and 5G-IANA research projects offer N.Apps through Helm Charts, deployed

on Kubernetes clusters, hence offered as Kubernetes Pods [5]. Additionally, when N.Apps are offered through the NFV paradigm, their orchestration is achieved by leveraging a NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), which relies on a NFV Infrastructure (NFVI) controlled by a Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM). According to T. Panagiotis, et al. [6], by 2020, the most employed open-source NFVOs were: OSM, ONAP, SONATA, and Cloudify. Contrastingly, cloud-native N.Apps deployment can be achieved by directly invoking Kubernetes APIs, which is a more straightforward approach that gives developers more freedom, as followed by E. Liotou et al. [5]

The various approaches to orchestrate Network Applications also impact how the applications are packaged and offered. While Kubernetes-deployed applications may be packaged as Helm Charts, NFV-based applications follow more complex packaging conventions, aligned with specific information models. Therefore, using well-established standards supported by existing NFVOs is essential. Despite this, agnostic models can also be employed to describe NFV-based N.Apps, as long as they are later parsed to the information models supported by the NFVOs. This approach was followed by P. Twamley et al. [7], that proposed an advanced packaging format beyond existing NFV packaging concepts, yet fully backwards compatible with ETSI's NFV packages.

Some frameworks for testing and validating N.Apps also support the onboarding of testing artifacts, as suggested by M. Femminella [8]. For instance, on the 5G EVE Project platform it is possible to onboard several testing blueprints [8]. Similarly, the 5GTANGO Verification and Validation platform allows N.App developers to onboard various test plugins, such as docker images [3].

Given the complexity of the Network Application packages, the testing workflows may also consider some initial validations on them. These validations should occur between onboarding and deployment, focusing on artifact integrity, compliance with standards, and security [3]. This is the case of the validation pipeline suggested in [9]. This testing pipeline is static, only performing a strict test case collection aimed at validating if N.App packages are correctly structured.

If the packages validation step is successful, the N.App can be deployed. After a N.App is successfully deployed, the execution of test cases to evaluate its behavior and functionality may start. These tests should address the N.App's behavior, performance, interoperability, scalability, availability, security, privacy, and interaction with the 5G network's control plane [3]. The Linux Foundation's view aligns with these test scopes since it has introduced over 200 requirements for N.App component implementation, focusing on design, resiliency, security, and modularity.

In regards to performance benchmarking, one should evaluate the N.Apps response time, throughput compliance, and how many User Equipments (UEs) can be connected with the Network Application without hindering its performance [10]. On the other hand, security testing should encompass an evaluation of the application code and binaries, fraud detection mechanisms, and logging, while also addressing privacy aspects [11].

To thoroughly validate a N.App, a detailed process, encompassing test cases, their implementation, and their execution is crucial. Regarding the implementation of test cases, different authors propose different approaches. While some approaches involve implementing test cases as SSH command collections [12], M. Peuster et al. [3] suggests that N.App

developers create custom test plugins as docker images. However, both methods require developers to provide full access to their applications, potentially exposing trade secrets. Therefore, novel N.App validation methodologies and frameworks are needed.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR TESTING N.APPS

To thoroughly address the testing and validation of 5G Network Applications, a comprehensive framework is required. We now propose a comprehensive architecture for such framework that is aligned with the various dimensions of testing N.Apps. This architecture is illustrated in Figure 1. It integrates a 5G infrastructure and advanced orchestration capabilities to deploy N.Apps and testing processes. Additionally, it should include a testing layer that offers test orchestration and provides the various testing artifacts. Monitoring capabilities are also essential, as they allow to compute the N.Apps footprint and validate KPIs. Additionally, a testing framework should also support collecting logs from the N.Apps and host infrastructure. Lastly, the testing framework should support multi-domain capabilities.

Next, we outline the actors involved in the operation and management of such framework, and detail the components of the architecture presented in Figure 1.

A. Actors

The management and operation of a framework designed for testing 5G Network Applications should involve, at least, the following key actors: N.App Developers, N.App Testers, and Facility Managers.

The N.App Developers are responsible for developing vertical or cross-vertical N.Apps. Thus, they need access to a Portal to onboard their applications and other artifacts. Additionally, this Portal must provide mechanisms to orchestrate applications on the testbed. Still, the N.App Developers cannot trigger the deployment of a N.App by themselves, since they can only make a deployment request, which must be authorized by a Facility Manager. After the deployment of a N.App, the Portal should inform the developer and provide a detailed log of the orchestration operations.

N.App Testers are in charge of configuring and triggering testing and validation processes. They need access to the Portal for onboarding test cases and Experiment Descriptors, which are artifacts that outline all test cases that must be executed. Additionally, Testers should be able to request the orchestration of N.Apps and testing processes.

Finally, Facility Managers are responsible for managing the different facilities involved in the testing of N.Apps. They require access to the portal to enumerate resources, oversee scheduling, and monitor facility-related resources. They should also coordinate multi-domain orchestration scenarios as they may be required by some N.Apps.

B. Components

We now address the core components that should comprise a framework for testing Network Applications, like the one illustrated in Figure 1.

Since we aim to design a framework for orchestrating and testing 5G Network Applications, the most important component is the 5G Network. The sites where the N.Apps are tested must offer a 5G Core, New Radio RAN, and an efficient transport

Fig. 1. Proposed Architecture

network between them. We propose offering at least 5G Release 17, since it provides enough support for Extended Reality, Industrial IoT, and Vehicle-to-Everything use cases, which may capitalize on 5G N.Apps.

The previously introduced Portal serves as an Operations Support System (OSS), ensuring seamless orchestration, management, and coordination of Network Applications and resources across the various facilities. This component must support operations like (i) onboarding N.App and testing artifacts, (ii) orchestrating N.Apps and testing processes, (iii) listing testing reports, (iv) enumerating available test cases, and (v) consulting deployment logs. Hence, it is the framework’s entry point for the various actors.

A Continuous Integration (CI) Service must also be considered to handle the orchestration and coordination of the testing processes. It must also collect test results and generate a Test Report, to be published on the OSS. Moreover, the integration between the CI Service and the OSS should allow for fully automated N.App testing and validation processes.

Since the proposed framework may involve multiple facilities, the CI Service must be capable of steering testing processes to the facility/facilities that host the N.Apps. Therefore, it should be aided by distributed Testing Execution Agents (TEAs) that reside in the different facilities. TEAs receive testing processes from the CI Service Testing Orchestrator, executing them and collecting their results. TEAs can be placed in the same L2 network as the N.App or at the RAN to mimic 5G UE interactions. It is also essential that the TEAs can access the repositories that store the various test cases. While the OSS hosts custom tests onboarded by N.App Testers, each facility should have its own Local Test Repository (LTR) for N.App agnostic tests.

Each facility requires an orchestrator to handle instantiation requests from the OSS. NFV-based N.Apps deployment relies on an NFVO, while Cloud-Native N.Apps rely on a Cloud-Native N.App Orchestrator (CNNO). While the NFVO relies on a NFVI to deploy the N.Apps, the CNNO relies on a Cloud-Native Infrastructure (CNI).

The previous components, combined with the core OSS, provide a comprehensive framework for the orchestration of Network Applications. However, the main objective of the proposed framework is to allow for the testing and validation of N.Apps. Therefore, additional testing components are required.

One of the most important functionalities that N.Apps must

offer is the capability of interacting with the control plane of a network. Therefore, it should be validated if N.Apps can interact with 5G Control Plane Network Functions like the Policy Control Function (PCF) or the Network Exposure Function (NEF). One approach to test this interaction is to forward all requests from the N.Apps to the 5G System through a monitoring component, which logs all interactions. However, encryption/security mechanisms may compromise it. Another approach is to use simulators for the 5G Network Functions, which can record and propagate the requests to the real 5G System. Thus, each testing facility should have various 5G Network Function Simulators.

Another crucial capability of a N.App validation framework is the ability to monitor the resources used by the various applications. This monitoring helps infer the resources required for the operation of a 5G N.App. A comprehensive framework should support at least two levels of monitoring: (i) 5G resources consumed by the N.App and (ii) computing resources consumed by each N.App component.

Monitoring the consumption of 5G resources can be accomplished using a dedicated monitoring stack that tracks the resources utilized by the 5G Core Network Functions. Moreover, this stack can be complemented by a man-in-the-middle component that monitors the traffic exchanged between the Network Applications and the 5G Core NFs. On the other hand, the monitoring of the computing resources consumed by each N.App component presents a simpler challenge, as there are many out-of-the-box monitoring stacks that can meet this need.

In addition to monitoring, a comprehensive testing framework should offer logging capabilities. These capabilities should enable the collection and subsequent analysis of both N.App and infrastructure logs. N.App-level logs provide valuable insights into the operations executed by an N.App, offering a means to troubleshoot any erroneous behaviors. In parallel, infrastructure logs allow for a better understanding of how the infrastructure supports and responds to the operations initiated by the N.App, particularly those impacting the 5G infrastructure.

Therefore, testing frameworks should provide built-in and transparent log collectors that can be leveraged by N.Apps to publish their logs. Moreover, these frameworks should not only enable log collection but also offer tools for log analysis. Such tools allow to simplify log interpretation, aiding N.App developers and testers in deriving insights from the collected information.

Finally, to achieve a testing and orchestration framework

that can support multi-domain experiments, a multi-domain orchestrator is required. This orchestrator should negotiate the establishment of overlay networks between the different testing facilities, therefore enabling a secure communication between N.App components placed at different geographic places. This multi-domain orchestrator can be integrated in the core OSS or offered as an ad-hoc component.

C. Testing Methodology

As previously stated in Section II, various testing frameworks/platforms [3] [7] [8] delegate the implementation of test cases to the N.App developers. This approach allows developers to design, onboard, and execute custom tests to validate the custom behavior of their N.Apps. However, given that many N.Apps share similar capabilities (e.g. the capability of interacting with a 5G NEF), test cases could also be shared by different N.Apps. Therefore, a testing framework should support two types of test cases: developer-defined test cases and N.App agnostic testcases. While the developer-defined test cases are implemented by the N.App developers and testers themselves, the agnostic tests should be offered out-of-the-box by the testing framework. Considering this, the agnostic tests should be highly parameterized to allow for their usage under various testing processes.

Regarding the aspects that should be tested, M. Pasteur et al. suggested to address N.Apps' behavior, performance, interoperability, scalability, availability, security, privacy, and interaction with the 5G network's control plane [3]. When considering only N.App agnostic tests, it is not possible to address some of these aspects. The behavior and interoperability of N.App are intrinsic to the application itself. Thus, developer-defined tests are required to perform these validation, as only the N.App developers and testers are aware of the internals of their applications, and know what is their desired behavior. Contrastingly, performance, scalability, availability, security, and interaction with the 5G network's control plane are aspects that can be validated through agnostic tests. Therefore, testing frameworks should offer out-of-the-box test cases to validate these aspects. Still, N.App developers should be free to also implement custom tests to evaluate these aspects. The conjunction of agnostic tests with developer-defined tests, allows for more robust testing processes, leading to more reliable N.Apps.

When implementing test cases to be offered by a testing framework, it is of utmost importance that these tests do not require access to privileged information, as doing so results in an additional risk of exposing trade secrets. Therefore, N.App agnostic tests should be as non-invasive as possible. This approach allows for added trust between N.App developers and the testing platform, as they are not prompted to share secret information (e.g. SSH or API credentials) with the platform. Still, developers should be able perform invasive testing through the test cases they develop.

Finally, after a Network Application has undergone a testing process, the testing framework should collect all test results, testing reports, and testing logs. These artifacts should be transparently made available to the N.App developers and testers. Additionally, a testing process report summarizing the testing outcomes should be created and offered to both testers and developers.

IV. THE 5GASP TESTING FRAMEWORK

Based on the framework's proposed architecture, we now discuss its implementation under the 5GASP European Research Project. This section then addresses the implementation of 5GASP's Testing Framework to orchestrate, test and validate N.Apps.

The OSS, implemented with Openslice (OSL) [13], adopts a service-oriented architecture aligned with 3GPP and ETSI standards, while leveraging TM Forum (TMF) OpenAPIs to onboard and orchestrate Network Slices, Applications, and Network Functions. Moreover, OSL supports the onboarding of NFV and Cloud-Native Applications and interacts with various orchestrators to orchestrate them.

The onboarding of N.App and Testing Artifacts must be aligned with OSL's TMF APIs. Therefore, we consider N.Apps and testing processes as Services within OSL. Moreover, TMF supports simple Services or bundled ones, which allows to represent experimentation/testing processes as bundled Services that comprise the orchestration of the N.App and the testing execution. Additionally, we may consider another service for the orchestration of a Network Slice that shall host the N.App. Thus, we adopted a N.App onboarding bundle composed by: the N.App Artifacts, the Network Slice Specification, and the optional Testing Artifacts [14].

The described bundle provides the means for the N.App Developers and Testers to request the orchestration of N.Apps and testing processes. Additionally, by leveraging the N.App onboarding bundle, N.App Developers and Testers can request for their applications to be onboarded on top of a custom designed Network Slice. To this end, they must onboard a Network Slice Template aligned with GSMA's Generic Slice Template [15]. This approach is highly relevant for both developers and testers, as it allows to test and experiment with N.Apps under various network scenarios. Moreover, this capability is not observed in the testing frameworks presented in Section II.

For the orchestration of a N.App to take place at a facility, OSL must interact with its orchestrators. Given that OSL is already prepared to interact with NFVOs through the SOL0005 standard, we opted to install Open-Source MANO (OSM) in the different facilities. OSM is an ETSI-NFV compliant Management and Orchestration framework that exposes a SOL0005-standardized API. Moreover, OSM can deploy N.Apps on both Openstack and Kubernetes. Thus, if N.Apps are offered as cloud-native applications, they can be wrapped around a NFV data models and deployed by OSM.

The integration between OSL and OSM guarantees the orchestration of N.Apps, whether they follow an NFV approach or cloud-native. Still, more components are needed for comprehensive testing and validation of N.Apps. One of these components is the CI Service Testing Orchestrator. This component orchestrates testing processes based on a testing blueprint onboarded by the N.App Testers, and was implemented using the FastAPI Framework. The testing blueprint must be onboarded via the onboarding bundle, as part of the testing artifacts. This blueprint, named 5GASP Testing Descriptor, is a YAML file that enumerates all test cases (agnostic and developer-defined) that should be executed, as well as values for the input parameters of each test case. More information of the 5GASP Testing Descriptor is available in [14].

Regarding the test cases, our platform offers tests implemented using the Robot Framework, which automatically generates report and log files in HTML, for an easy visualization. However, the 5GASP Testing Framework can also support other testing tools. For executing test cases, each facility requires at least one Testing Execution Agent. These agents are made available through Jenkins since it provides a straightforward API for submitting pipeline configuration files. These files contain information on how to collect, execute, and gather outputs from the various test cases, and are generated on-demand by the CI Service Test Orchestrator, which submits them to the TEAs via Jenkins' API.

The first stage of the testing process is obtaining the test cases, either from the testbed's LTR, or from OSL. While the LTR hosts the agnostic test cases, OSL provides custom tests for specific N.Apps, onboarded by N.App Testers and Developers. After the TEAs collect and execute all test cases, they aggregate all testing outputs and send them to the CI Service. The CI Service then creates a visual testing report on OSL, making it accessible to N.App Testers.

Additionally, to support a wider range of testing scopes, the facilities involved in the testing processes also offer a NEF Simulator – NEFSim [16]. This component offers a standardized NEF northbound API, allowing N.App Developers to experiment with NEF's APIs. This way, N.App Developers can implement NEF clients in their applications, without requiring access to a full-blown NEF. Considering that the NEF is the gateway to the 5G System, if a N.App can correctly interact with the NEF, then it can also interact with the 5G System. Therefore, NEFSim can aid in ensuring N.Apps can interact with a 5G System.

The 5GASP Testing Framework also offers monitoring data. We monitor the computing and network resource usage of N.App components using Prometheus and Grafana. Prometheus scrapes metrics from Openstack and Kubernetes, and Grafana presents them. Additionally, 5G-specific metrics are collected from a proprietary solution that monitors the testbed's 5G System – the 5GAIner infrastructure [17]. This infrastructure offers an Huawei commercial-grade Standalone (SA) 5G Network, featuring Huawei 5G New Radio cells suitable for both outdoor and indoor scenarios. This network includes a 5G SA Core compliant with 3GPP Release 17 standards. Additionally, we also provide measurements on the 5G resources consumed by each N.App through a man-in-the-middle monitoring switch [18] that sits between the NFVI/CNI and the 5G System. This switch handles all interactions between N.Apps and 5G UEs/Clients, allowing for N.App KPIs validation. Specifically, this switch enables the monitoring of the throughput, RTT, jitter and packets lost percentage between N.Apps and respective client UEs at the RAN.

Finally, our framework supports testing multi-domain N.Apps by relying on NetOr [19], a network orchestrator that deploys Wireguard tunnels between different domains. NetOr leverages OSM to deploy Wireguard servers in various facilities and establishes a Virtual Private Network mesh among all facilities.

Together, these components and technologies result in a framework for orchestrating, testing, and validating 5G N.Apps. A diagram its implementation is showcased in Figure 2.

A. Test Cases

As previously stated in Section III-C, performance, scalability, availability, security, and interaction with the 5G network's

control plane are aspects that can be validated through agnostic tests. Therefore, the 5GASP Testing Framework offers various test cases that address such aspects. We defined different testing scopes to cover the various dimensions crucial to the testing and validating 5G N.Apps. The testing scopes we have identified are the following: (i) 5G Readiness, (ii) Security & Privacy, (iii) Performance & Scalability, and (iv) Availability & Continuity.

The 5G Readiness testing scope focuses on evaluating the N.Apps' ability to interact with the 5G network components such as the NEF and PCF, ensuring they can leverage the advanced capabilities of 5G networks. Thus, this scope addresses the interoperability and integration aspects that are crucial to achieve seamless communication and operation within the 5G System. On the other hand, Security & Privacy testing aims to ensure that N.Apps comply with the desired security requirements. Since 5G networks handle sensitive and critical data across various sectors, it is paramount to guarantee the N.Apps security and privacy. The validation of such aspects results in higher N.App security and privacy standards, therefore protecting user data and maintaining users trust. The Performance & Scalability scope examines the N.Apps' capability to sustain optimal performance under varying traffic loads. This testing scope ensures that applications can scale efficiently without compromising on performance, which is essential for applications in scenarios such as smart cities and autonomous vehicles. Finally, the Availability & Continuity testing scope measures the N.Apps' resilience over time, particularly under demanding scenarios like transmission impairments and high service demands. This testing scope is crucial for applications where downtime or interruptions can have serious consequences, ensuring that N.Apps provide a reliable and uninterrupted service to their clients.

These testing axis were chosen because they focus on the most critical aspects of 5G N.Apps functionality and reliability. Still, other testing scopes could exist. For future implementation, we consider addressing the energy efficiency of N.Apps, as well as the their overall user experience. However, these aspects are secondary, since they are influenced by factors such as security, performance, or availability. Thus, we consider that by prioritizing the described four testing scopes, we can ensure that N.Apps are robust, secure, and capable of delivering high performance demanding 5G environments.

We now present the different test cases that were implemented for each testing scope. These tests can be observed on Table I and their detailed implementation and documentation found at https://github.com/5gasp/CICD_LTR.

B. Experimentation

To validate the 5GASP Testing Framework, we conducted tests on 11 N.Apps. These N.Apps were developed by the 5GASP project consortium and address various vertical sectors, such as the automotive and public safety ones. To test each N.App, we selected a collection of test cases from different scopes. Additionally, 5 N.Apps were also tested using developer-defined tests. Even though we do not showcase the results of the described testing processes, these can be found at [20]. This document not only addresses the results of the described testing processes, but also showcases the collected testing logs.

We highlight the results obtained for the Fire Detection and Ground Assistance Using Drones N.App, which was tested with

Fig. 2. The 5GASP Testing Framework

TABLE I
AGNOSTIC TEST CASES AVAILABLE AT THE 5GASP TESTBED

5G Readiness Testing Scope			
Acquisition of Serving Cell Information	Acquisition of UE Handover Event	Acquisition of UE Path Loss	Acquisition of QoS Sustainability
Acquisition of UE Location	Authentication with 5GS	Acquisition of UE Received Signal Power Information	
Security & Privacy Testing Scope			
N. App Package Integrity	Secure SSH Credentials	Openstack Port Security	SSL Protected APIs
SBOM Security Report	Vulnerability Security Report	Open Ports	SSH Server Security
Protected/Encrypted Interfaces		N.App Uses a Valid Security-Group	
Performance & Scalability Testing Scope			
E2E Download/Upload Throughput & Latency - Single UE	E2E Download/Upload Throughput & Latency - Multiple UE	NEF Signaling Performance - Maximum Number of Connections	NEF Signaling Performance - Requests Per Second
NEF Signaling Performance - Response Time	Radio Access Network Monitoring	N.App Static Page - Performance	N.App APIs - Response Time
N.App APIs - Requests per Second	N.App APIs - Maximum Number of Connections	IP Round-Trip Time	IP Traceroute
Availability & Continuity Testing Scope			
N. App Keeps Operating after a Restricted Bandwidth Scenario	N. App Keeps Operating after an Introduced Delay Scenario	N. App Keeps Operating after an Introduced Packet Loss Scenario	N. App Keeps Operating after a Total Disruption of Communication
N. App Keeps Operating after an Introduced Packet Corruption Scenario			

test cases from all 4 testing scopes: all test cases (7) from the 5G readiness testing scope, 1 security and privacy test case, all test cases (11) from the performance and scalability axis, and all availability and continuity tests (5). The reduced amount of security and privacy tests relates to the fact that this N.App is offered as cloud-native application, and thus many security evaluations do not apply. This is due to the fact that many security controls are enforced by Kubernetes at the infrastructure level rather than by the application itself. Contrastingly, the Virtual On-Board Unit Provisioning N.App, offered through Virtual Machines, was evaluated with 7 test cases from the

security and privacy testing scope. These experiments allowed us to validate the methodologies applied in the proposed testbed.

C. Comparison With Other Testing Frameworks

We now compare our Testing Frameworks with other state-of-the-art Testing Frameworks, addressed in Section II.

Starting with test cases that shall support the validation processes, our framework enables developers and testers to onboard their custom tests, as well as using agnostic ones, already provided by the framework. This is not seen in the Testing Frameworks presented in [3] [7] [8] [9], since they do not provide any agnostic test cases that can be used to test various N.Apps. Additionally, the test cases provided by our framework are implemented with the Robot Framework, which produces detailed logs of the test execution. Our framework also supports custom test cases developed with other technologies, for instance simple python or SSH scripts. This is another advantage of our framework: the fact that test cases implementation is not tied to any specific technology. In contrast, frameworks such as the 5G EVE one [8] demand for developers to develop tests through SSH scripts. The Testing Framework proposed by M. Pasteur [3] also ties developers to the usage of docker to develop test cases.

The agnostic test cases, already implemented and offered by our Testing Framework, also expedite the testing of N.Apps. By having access to already implemented test cases, N.App developers and testers may sooner start the testing of their N.Apps. Additionally, developers and testers can better understand how they can implement their custom tests by analyzing the implementation of the agnostic test cases, since these there open source and accessible to the public.

Regarding orchestration capabilities, the presented testing framework enables the orchestration of both NFV and cloud-native applications, all while offering automated testing pipelines to validate these applications. While the framework presented in [5] also allows orchestrating cloud-native applications, its testing automation mechanisms fall short when compared to the ones offered by our framework.

A drawback of our testing framework is the fact that it does not provide any log collection and analysis component, what would be desirable. The same happens with all Testing Frameworks addressed in Section II. However, N.App developers can implement custom tests to collect N.App logs. This approach

is intrusive, but allows to surpass the lack of log collection mechanisms of our framework.

With respect to monitoring metrics, the 5GASP Testing Framework proved capable of collecting not only N.App metrics but also infrastructure-related ones. Collecting infrastructure metrics is also seen in other frameworks. The 5G EVE one [8] is the only collecting N.App metrics, which is achieved through the execution of SSH commands on the N.Apps and thus is an intrusive approach. Contrastingly, our framework provides built-in metrics collection mechanisms, which allow to transparently collect N.App-level metrics without requiring any configuration from the developers, as our monitoring probes are installed in the infrastructure that hosts the N.Apps.

Lastly, 5GASP's Testing Framework differs from other state-of-the-art ones by allowing N.App developers and testers to onboard Network Slice Templates. This approach allows developers and testers to configure the network capabilities that will be offered to their N.Apps during testing. This enables to test N.Apps under various network conditions, which is a capability not seen in any of the Testing Frameworks addressed in Section II.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The need for reliable, scalable, and secure applications will increase with the growth of 5G and future B5G/6G networks. The introduced 5GASP Testing Framework addresses this by supporting the orchestration and testing of both NFV-based and cloud-native N.Apps. Additionally, the integration of agnostic test cases, advanced orchestration, and monitoring tools ensures robust testing for security, performance, scalability, and 5G readiness, addressing the needs of various industries.

However, the presented framework requires additional work, particularly in terms of log collection and analysis. The integration of log collection and analysis in our framework would allow, for instance, Root Cause Analysis. By analyzing monitoring data, infrastructure, and N.App logs, the 5GASP Testing Framework could assist developers and testers in identifying the root cause for the erroneous behavior of a N.App. Despite this, as addressed in Section IV-C, our testing framework offers additional capabilities than other state-of-the-art ones, thus advancing the current state-of-the-art.

The research and development of advanced N.App testing frameworks such as this one will not only facilitate the design, implementation, and validation of N.Apps, but will also drive innovation by providing environments where novel use cases can be explored, thereby accelerating the adoption of future generation N.Apps.

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